

How the Human Resources Manager Can Be the Driving Element of Company Change

A success case study

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Abstract: In the world we live in today, more than ever, change occurs at an increasingly rapid pace and affects the most ordinary of citizens, and companies are no exception. Innovations occur at various levels and organizations are caught up in the current, becoming part of it, so it is up to them to equip themselves with the best resources to adapt and be successful.

In this context of market instability, it is important to understand how change can be managed at its best, minimizing negative impacts and maximizing positive ones. Therefore, the purpose of this work is related to understanding the importance of how the Human Resources Manager can be the driving force behind change. To this end, the focus is on the elements that the process should include and the connection that is established with Human Resources Management practices integrated into dimensions such as Change, Communication, Leadership, Training, among other aspects.

The methodology used was supported by a hybrid discovery study between qualitative analysis to detect the research problem and quantitative analysis to carry out the study.

In terms of findings, we were able to understand that having a clear purpose, training, motivation and leadership styles are the biggest influencers that human resources managers must consider performing the role of change agents.

The practical implication of this study is at the level of the application of its results, for the increasing development of the functions of human resources managers.

INTRODUCTION

In today's economy, from one point of view, opportunities are global, but from another point of view, the level of uncertainty and change is constant, and different countries are increasingly correlative. This new economy of ideas implies constant adaptation and even reinvention of the work environments themselves in order to achieve higher levels of performance. Expectations are so high for both organizations and the people who are part of them, because success has to be achieved in an extremely competitive environment.

From this perspective, management and the manager play an important role and it is therefore essential for future managers to equip themselves with the necessary knowledge and instruments that will allow them to overcome these challenges.

DESCRIPTION

The main objective of this work is to answer the question "HOW CAN THE HUMAN RESOURCES MANAGER BE THE DRIVING ELEMENT OF CHANGE?"

EXPLORATORY STUDY

This work aims to describe the historical evolution of human resources management; contextualize the importance of good change management in light of the evidence of the current context; describe organizational change, namely concepts, causes, nature, modalities, approaches and implementation process; check the role of human resource management and change-driving practices in terms of communication, change, leadership, training and human resource management

The relevance of the research question is related to the fact that the current recessive context, which, together with rapid scientific and technological evolution, has led to profound transformations in the market, which are reflected in new ways of working, communicating, and, ultimately, new ways of living. Therefore, companies, as an open and living system that influences and is influenced by its surroundings, must develop mechanisms that enable them to understand the market, diagnosing its current situation and outlining a strategy that meets its expectations.

CONTEXTUALIZATION OF THE THEME

HISTORICAL EVOLUTION OF HUMAN RESOURCES MANAGEMENT

The understanding of HRM has been following the evolution of economic, cultural and social thought, as well as the conditions of lived reality, since the end of the 19th century, when it was divided into 6 phases/stages by Torrington et al. (2011) cited by Martinez (2015).

Thus, in a 1st phase/stage, which began at the beginning of the 19th century, during which the free-market system was linked to the concept of paternalistic social justice, where attempts were made to find improvements in the living conditions of workers. In a 2nd phase/stage and based on Taylor's scientific management (1856 - 1915), the main transmitters for increasing both

efficiency and productivity are organizational structures, work organization and social relations. In a 3rd phase/stage, after World War II, linked to economic prosperity and the increase in union demands, Human Resources Management responded to a new reality with the improvement of working conditions and benefits for workers. In a 4th phase/stage, we see the introduction of quantitative indicators in management and new ICT, and HRM highlights management activities in the integration of work. In a 5th phase/stage, inserted in a sociological influence in the 70s, the term “personnel management” was removed and the expression “human resources management” emerged, thus giving greater relevance to the perspective of human resources and the adjustment of the different local cultures.

Finally, Martinez (2015) mentions the 6th phase/stage, which is currently in use, as “human resource management”, but due to labour relations, and the way in which ICTs have been changing labour relations and globalization itself, there is much talk of “people management” or “HRM 2.0”.

This progress has led these researchers to compare the new HRM model with employee performance.

EVOLUTION OF CHANGE MANAGEMENT

Economic crises, digital transformation, COVID-19, wars, and what's next now? Changes are undoubtedly inevitable, they are increasingly frequent, they are everywhere all the time. Today we do not live in the same world as 30 years ago, just as in 30 years we will be in a completely different world than today. It is not possible to escape change, since it is present in our lives, whether personal, professional, in politics, in society, or in technology. Here we are talking about organizational change and as the environment changes, companies also do so in order to conduct their business as a way to adapt, innovate and, above all, stand out. Often, an organization's chance of success is directly related to its ability to adapt to change and how quickly its employees accept and embrace those changes.

Change management is not just about writing about communication plans or strategies. This is a concept that is always evolving and its application in the world of organizations hovers between using understandings from the past and the present to execute change projects. Change management dates back to the early days, before the 1990s. The foundation of change management was to improve the collective understanding of human beings, how they experience change, and how they interact and react to change. This time had the contribution of different theorists who presented research and to understand changes, being: Arnold van Gennep (1909 - “change in three stages: separation from the current state, movement through transition and reincorporation into a future state”); Kurt Lewin (1948 - “stages of change: thaw, move, freeze”); Richard Bechar (1969 - “defining change management”); William Bridges (1979 - “stages of a transition: completion, neutral zone, new beginning”).

From 1990 to 2000 we can find change management “on the radar”. Here begins the understanding of the human side of change in project meetings and the concept itself begins to become visible among the most senior executives in

an organization and also among other members who make decisions in organizations. During this period, many of the principles that define the discipline of change management that still exists today were defined. Principles such as geopolitical forces, economic development, development of a new value system (“empowerment”) and the changing relationship between employee and employer will establish new strategies for an increased recognition of the importance of the human side in change. During this period, it was understood that individual changes would not be enough and could be sustained and guided in an organization if they were carried out with thoughtful and repeated decisions. The main contributions of this period came in the wake of: General Electric (1990 - “introduction of the change acceleration process as part of the improvement program); Daryl Conner (1992 - “brought reflections on numerous concepts and topics of change); Todd Jick (1993 - The Most Common Pitfalls and the 10 Commandments of Implementing Change); Jeanenne LaMarsh (1995 - ability to change, mitigating resistance to change, supporting change); John Kotter (1996 - The Eight Mistakes and the Eight Steps to Change); Spencer Johnson (1998 - how people can deal with the changes happening around them).

Then, from the 2000s to the present day, we find the “formalization” of the change management discipline. Although the concepts date back many years, it was only from 2000 onwards that the discipline was formalized and accelerated specifically as change management. This formalization occurs in three aspects: processes and tools (more rigorous structures, more robust processes and tools were developed based on previously established concepts to support the consistent application of change management); positions and roles (organizations begin to create specific positions with the application of change management projects and initiatives) and finally organizational functions (organizations begin to establish functions and structures to support the application of change management in the organization as a whole). It was during this period that standards and certifications in change management emerged.

Regarding its future, it will continue on several fronts, namely: (integration with project management and innovation management and other topics such as circular economy, positive organizations, among others); focus on considering change management as an organizational competency (structured and intentional efforts to build individual change leadership competencies and to embed effective change practices into the organizational structure); and finally the individual development of change management professionals (certifications and design of personal skills).

It is understood that the discipline of change management continues to evolve and that new opportunities arise every day. However, many professionals and organizations still do not understand its importance, and do not yet have a structured process for it. Changes encompass the business environment, but above all, being focused on knowing how to deal with these

changes, beyond their essence, can be important for the development and renewal of the organization.

HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT AND CHANGE MANAGEMENT

HRM has evolved over time (20th century), whether theoretically or practically, subject to influences from the changing environment, “at the beginning of the 20th century, with the influence of labour relations and union movements that influenced the contents of HRM research, the designations of the activity and the emphases of the management practices themselves. This is the case in the current times, with the globalization of activities and businesses in which the contingency of theoretical and intervention options reveal the determining weight of contextual factors” (Neves and Gonçalves, 2009).

The fullness that marked the end of the 19th century and the first half of the 20th century, with the emergence of enormous industrial mass production units, with the invention of Henry Ford's assembly lines (Camara et al., 2007) and the approaches to the rationalization of work and business administration processes of Taylor and Fayol (Brandão and Parente, 1998; Drucker et al. 1998:20), and the expansion of colonial and inter-Atlantic trade was interrupted by World War I (1914-1918), which transformed the composition of the workforce, with the mass mobilization of men for war, with women taking on the majority of the functioning of the productive structure (Camara et al., 2007).

With the Great Depression or even the crisis of 1929, with the emergence of totalitarianism that would lead to the Second World War for 6 years (1939-1945), of which the destruction of European infrastructure, the terrible loss of human lives and the division of the continent into two large parts stand out. Then came years marked by reconstruction, decolonization and the creation of a common market.

With the growth of the old continent driven by the EEC and the preservation of a climate of peace, the expansion of well-being was made possible in the 1960s, which would later experience some disruptions in the 1970s due to the oil shocks in 1973/74 and 1978/79, which, by their nature, proved to be short-lived.

Subsequently, with the rapid development of ICT and with special attention to the internet, it led to new ways of relating organizations with markets and new systems of operation for organizations, changing some traditional ways of working (relationships and habits). Change is an indisputable truth, it is not easy to show, it is easy to reveal where it comes from, how it can affect the lives of people and organizations, and consequently, employees.

The beginning of the 21st century was marked by events of great importance, such as the September 11, 2001 attacks in the United States, the spread of terrorism throughout much of the world, radical Islam, the emergence of new economies, the BRIC, the acronym that encompasses Brazil and Russia, countries that stand out for their strategic raw materials, India, which is a centre of information and development in IT, and China itself, which has become one of the largest industrial economies on a global scale.

Given its historical moment, the influence of events on the lives of organizations and people can be seen, according to Rhinesmith (1996) “the post-World War II period would mark the turning point in the development of science and technology with theories, methods and scientific applications having a significant impact on the speed, dimension and ease of what we do. However, it is important to note that the methods of social sciences and adult education that support people's orientation to deal with rapid scientific changes are based on tools that date back to the 1950s and 1960s in terms of recruitment and selection, training, compensation and benefits systems and career progression, highlighting the gap between changes in the theory and technology of personnel development and those felt in science and technology.

In the 20th century, in the 1970s, there was a change in organizational patterns, also to new forms of work organization (NFOT), an expression used at the time, with special attention to the human factor and integrated into the current humanization of work (Kovács, 2006), the practice of organizational development with special attention to the environment, organization, social group and individual (Chiavenato, 1983 cit in Brandão and Parente, 2009), pointing to the logical control and planning of organizational change processes by promoting participation and the internal flow of information itself, with a view to individual and group learning and development.

Thus, with the different contextualization of the different authors and possible historical moments, it is necessary to understand that in a modern organization, there are new challenges that arise in the HR function, according to Camara et al. (2007), namely, consultancy, monitoring (Coaching), facilitation which is subdivided into organizational development and change management, among other aspects. The same author, Camara et al. (2007:72) also highlights that “in parallel, the person responsible for human resources management must seek to encourage an organizational climate that prepares and creates an appetite for change. Change is, in itself, a process that generates insecurity and stress in the people involved, and it is essential to create and maintain the necessary momentum for it to take off and continue, without hesitation or risk of regression.”

ORGANIZATIONAL CHANGE AND HUMAN RESOURCES MANAGEMENT

As was noticeable, the evolution of the HRM function was regulated by changes in the environment that helped to drive it. As seen, the theme of change is not exactly recent and according to history and various factors, depending on time and space, many references have been made to this social phenomenon that has triggered a multidisciplinary analysis as the main center of reflection in areas such as management, sociology, and psychosociology of organizations.

However, the different theories and thoughts linked to organizational change and development processes, coming from different points of interest, which often reach a divide of perspectives that do not value each other and produce isolated research, whose divided and partial analyses about an aggregate reality that cannot be separated are shown to be deficient. Thus, by

complementing each other, the different perspectives will allow for a greater understanding of organizational life, given that any theoretical perspective necessarily offers a partial explanation of the overall phenomenon.

A huge increase in publications alluding to the theme of change is one that has attracted the greatest interest in the area of social sciences, as witnessed by computer research by Van de Ven and Poole (1995) cited in Cunha et al. (2005), from which they listed more than a million articles with the descriptions change/development and, through a search carried out by Galpin (2000) of just one database, restricted to material published since January 1994, from which 1789 articles or books on the theme of change were identified. By way of parenthesis, Galpin (2000) concludes that, "from the review of this material, it focuses predominantly on analytical aspects of a practical and tangible nature (e.g., cost-benefit analysis, cost per unit, time cycle) and the bibliographic review of soft aspects of change is of a conceptual, theoretical or casuistic nature, barely covering useful indications for operationalization".

Change can be a word that is used too often in speeches of various natures, mainly political, business and academic. Firstly, change arouses interest as a phenomenon susceptible to intervention and control, while the approaches inspire and support the idea of change management.

"The growing importance and continued relevance of the topic establish a relationship of direct proportionality with the increase in market volatility, presenting itself as a backdrop in the organizational universe, since all areas of organizational sciences essentially aim at understanding the factors and conditions that facilitate change, so that, regardless of the objective that is intended to be achieved, change is the area that most attracts and concerns contemporary managers" (Cunha et al., 2005), which is due in particular to its character, which is both omnipresent and transversal.

CONCEPT OF CHANGE

Change can be conceptualized, according to Chiavenato, (2008, p. 12) as "the passage from one state to another. It is the transition from one situation to a different one. Change always represents transformation, alteration, modification, disturbance, interruption, fracture or rupture." We can also conceptualize change, according to Fernandez Gatti (2007), as "the capacity that organizations have to adapt to transformations required by endogenous and exogenous forces, through learning, which translates into a new structure or new behaviour for the organization".

Heraclitus states that "the only certainty we can have is that change is permanent." With good humor, Chiavenato (idem, 5), adds to that certainty, "death and taxes". Today, if it doesn't change, at the very least, it represents a lack of market share due to the lack of insertion of new technologies, trends and competitiveness.

The way in which all of us and organizations have adapted to changes over time, there has been a difference in the speed at which it occurs, however, in essence, it has always been carried out with the same objectives: survival.

Changes at the organizational level can be seen as:

- Technological, with changes in production processes for products;
- Products, with their development and changes, according to the new needs of customers or even with a focus on the development of different products, in order to conquer new markets;
- Structures with changes in the structural characteristics and the organization's own procedures;
- People and culture, in terms of changes in people's ways of thinking and acting and the internalization of new values and norms;
- Strategy, with changes in the organization's vision, goals and strategies.

CAUSES AND FACTORS

The authors indicate several origins of change, which they designate, sometimes as causes, sometimes as factors, some of which coincide in being grouped into four major dimensions or pillars, of a technological, economic, sociocultural and political nature (Fombrun, 1984 cit in Caetano and Tavares, 2000; Kovacs in Rodrigues, 1997: 12) - cit THE ROLE OF HUMAN RESOURCES MANAGEMENT IN CHANGE MANAGEMENT IN ORDER TO LEVERAGE ORGANIZATIONAL STRATEGY - Ana Sara Crispim Conceição Silva - Master's Project in Management, in particular the PEST analysis.

According to Fombrun (1984) cit in Caetano and Tavares (2000), "the factors that have had a preponderant power of influence are of a technological nature - notably technological innovations in the production of information; economic - with regard to market (im)balances and macroeconomic indicators; sociocultural - regarding new values and attitudes towards work and the vision of the social role of organizations in society and politics - considering that decision-making conditions business activity, whether directly or indirectly.

Thus, the change can have numerous causes, according to Camara et al. (2007) standardizes according to Robbins' idea that elucidates four factors of change, being: "the nature of the workforce, new technologies, economic shocks, and globalization and competition".

Starting with the nature of the workforce, it is notable that this is rooted in the change in values and attitudes of generations towards work, more specifically loyalty, where 50-year-old workers are loyal to their bosses, 40-year-olds are loyal to themselves and the younger they are, the more loyal their career plans are (Camara et al., 2007). The young workforce, with different aspirations and less loyalty, requires new responses that guarantee motivation, since the mobility of workers, especially of managers who do not hesitate to change employers in search of conditions that come closer to their expectations, is a reality.

NATURE

Change appears daily in the organizational world, at the end of the 20th century, promoted by transformations of endogenous and exogenous origin, presenting "(...) dynamic, almost omnipresent processes, often continuous in organizational contexts that face the instability, uncertainty and variability of a globalized world economy and in the face of which companies have to position

themselves and act, respond and/or anticipate the transformations underway” (Parente, 2006)

In this way, “change can have an endogenous or exogenous origin” (Parente, 2006), “with internal or external changes coexisting” (Rodrigues, 1998), “which can be grouped into intrinsic and extrinsic” (Camara et al., 2007), and it can be seen that these authors propose that change is provoked by causes that come from the organizational spectrum, or even outside it, with different nomenclatures.

According to Rodrigues (1998), various authors suggest that “organizational change can be seen as a management instrument and cannot be neglected, since internal and external changes coexist and are systematically integrated in the organization, hence they are presented as a management exercise that must have a holistic character in order to be successful, otherwise it runs the risk of becoming simplistic and poor from the point of view of the analysis of the phenomenon”.

According to Camara et al. (2007), “the main causes of change can be classified according to two major dimensions, namely, intrinsic and extrinsic causes.

Intrinsic changes are triggered to correct weaknesses in the functioning of the structure, standards and way of providing work that harm the good activity of the organization and its competitiveness.

Extrinsic changes, in turn, have their origin in transformations of the environment, particularly in the political, legal, economic, demographic, social and technological spheres, which have repercussions, for example, in changes in consumption habits, lifestyles, the emergence of substitute products or services, among others”.

TYPES OF CHANGE

Having identified the causes and factors, it is now important to assess the types of change, that is, how it develops in the organizational environment, what are the required capabilities and skills, and the organizational tools.

All the factors mentioned above, such as the increase in the diffusion of ICT, the saturation of the durable goods market, market differentiation, high management costs, difficulties in the functioning of large companies and, above all, the instability of the global production system in a global economy, have contributed to the organizational patterns based on stability and predictability becoming unsustainable. Therefore, the search for new organizational standards with the aim of reducing costs, improving quality and increasing flexibility has become an important condition for the survival of companies.

Flexibility affects a flexible organization, whether in production or work organization, and is characterized by “(...) little formalization, connection and/or integration of the various functions (...) production planning and operational decisions decentralized at the level of work groups. Qualified operators are versatile, that is, they carry out a range of activities with a high degree of autonomy (...) mutual adjustment constitutes the main regulatory

mechanism. Working relationships characterized by dialogue and cooperation. Remuneration is based on qualifications...” (Kovács, 1989 cit in Rodrigues, 1998:37), in a democratic and participatory vision, highlighting the characteristic versatility and autonomy and the emphasis on greater commitment.

CHANGE PROCESS

According to (Katz & Kahn, 1978 cited in Cunha et al., 2005) “The process of change, metaphorically represents a journey from state A (current) to state B (desired and desirable) and can be triggered by several reasons that can arise from the action of several stimuli, namely, detection of a gap/disruption between expected and verified results, introduction of interruptions in organizational cycles or monitoring of the environment by institutional leaders”.

The authors (Van de Ven and Poole, 1995; Nadler et al., 1995; Rodrigues, 1998, Hooper and Potter, 2003; Camara et al., 2007) “only refer to the change process as an alteration to the status quo, immediately referring to the criticality of the process, as it involves “leaving the comfort zone” and rethinking policies, practices, work methods, among others, which can generate antibodies on the part of the various organizational actors, giving rise to resistance to change”.

According to Camara et al., (2007), “the process of change, regardless of how it occurs, whether planned or imposed, is based on the current situation, status quo, which is not satisfactory and represents a reason for frustration so that the need to change is felt. The objective of the process is to correct dissatisfaction by establishing a desirable horizon that one wishes to achieve, an attractive and appealing future vision that appears as the path to success.” Currently, between these two aspects, there is a transitional phase that requires strong leadership to follow the direction and pace of change. This procedure must especially consider the timing of the adaptation, to the point of not being too slow and causing a desire to retreat, nor too fast so that there are no losses along the way, nor that there is a “(...) risk of distortions or misrepresentations in the objectives, which represent an uncontrollable change in trajectory”.

Parente (2006), in a more simplistic view, agrees with the process of change illustrated by Camara et al. (2007:248), proposing the characterization of change processes by a series of phases, being, “(...) (i) recognition of its need at an initial moment, in which it is decided or forced to carry it out; (ii) the moments of implementation, defined as transition periods from one state to another; (iii) the final state, in which the transformation is considered to have been completed (or not), in whole or in part. It should be noted, however, that this description is lacking in simplicity and linearity, typical of the closed economic context associated with growth cycles based on the business stability of the past, which today make it obsolete or deficient, and so change has become chameleon-like and is now defined as a continuous and progressive process, not always triggered intentionally and strategically, nor always

materialized in a final state representing a point of arrival. It is often a permanent and continuous state, in which the goals achieved with a change constitute the starting point for new developments and the new changes arise interconnected with intermediate phases of many other changes". The author herself informs that, regardless of whether they are intentional or not, the way these processes are managed can demonstrate an opportunity to force learning at the group and individual level, and this conditions individual internalization by associating favourable/adherent or even resistant behaviours. Overall, to conclude, it points to an anthropocentric vs. Technocentric, where the first is guided by the involvement of workers with the possibility of success, while the technocentric encourages a superficial adaptation of changes, due to its imposition.

ORGANIZATIONAL CHANGE MANAGEMENT MODELS

As previously mentioned, the first foundations and pioneering models of organizational change take us to Kurt Lewin, having subsequently undergone reformulations. The approach to planned change came from this same author, Lewin (1951) who speaks of the 3 steps of change, being: unfreezing - from the present level, movement - to a new level and refreezing - at the new level.

Subsequently, as referenced by Burnes (1992), there were authors who suggested analysing and improving Lewin's 3-step model, such as the author Lippin et al. (1958) who presented the 8-phase model and the author Bullock and Batten (1985) as previously explained developed a synthetic 4-phase model of planned change from an analysis of 30 models.

IMPLEMENTATION

According to Bullock and Batten (1985, cited in Burnes (1992)), "successful change interventions involve the movement of an organization through different stages in order to achieve a higher level of performance", with each stage requiring the application of certain procedures (methods and techniques). However, Burnes (1992) states that, "although the sequence and number of stages are relatively clear, the actual processes involved in response to specific problems and opportunities that organizations have faced over time, and therefore can be used to achieve a favourable outcome in a given situation, that is, for example, a team building technique may be a solution in one situation and be totally inappropriate in another".

Burnes (1992) states that "in order to overcome this difficulty, a series of authors proposed to classify the main techniques and methods related to the specific procedures that must be followed to guarantee the effectiveness of interventions, regardless of the methods and techniques that may be developed". Thus, according to Agyris (1970), the conditions that are necessary for the success of change are: "1) generating valid information, 2) providing freedom and enlightening alternatives to those involved, 3) creating a commitment on the part of those involved with the choices made. These ideas are defended by the author cited above, as part of any intervention activity, regardless of the objectives that are intended to be achieved. In this thought,

Burke et al. (1981) introduces another condition to the previous list, being “the importance of 4) operating a cultural change”

In order to achieve these four conditions previously mentioned, according to French and Bell (1984) cit in Burnes (1992) they consider that “the agent of change must structure his intervention process in order to ensure the following aspects:

- Involvement of everyone who will be affected by the problem or opportunity;
- The intervention is oriented towards the problems and opportunities identified by those involved;
- The objective and the path to be achieved are clear;
- There is a high probability of success;
- Contain both experience-based learning and conceptual/cognitive/theory-based learning;
- The climate of the activity is organized so that individuals are relaxed rather than anxious and defensive;
- Participants must both learn to solve a particular problem and learn “how to learn” simultaneously;
- Activities should be organized in such a way that individuals can learn both about the task (what the group is working on) and the process (how the group does it);
- Individuals are involved as whole people, not as segmented people, therefore demanding of an individual's work and the six thoughts, beliefs, feelings and ambitions must be called “into play”, so one should not only attend to one or two of these aspects”.

Camara et al. (2007), in turn, highlight “the need to fulfil certain prerequisites when implementing a change process in addition to those they consider fundamental, such as the characterization of the vision of the future, the identification of critical success factors and an action plan, referring to conditions such as communicating the vision to all workers in uninterrupted phases (cascade system) in order to enable them to analyse, improve and understand it with criticism and comments; the internalization of the need for change by the actors, their adherence and motivation to its implementation (financial, human and material)”.

Given the situation, as already discussed in the first phase, when one becomes aware of the need for change, it is important to highlight the aspects that arise as a sine-qua-non condition to enable a process of change, the diagnosis and resistance to change that appear from a practically inseparable point of view in the processes of change, in order to take preventive measures that cancel out a priori probable antibodies that may probably appear and that are often avoidable. Following these, all change values must be observed in the process.

METHODOLOGY

The conceptual framework is represented in figure 1, representing the sequence of the research study.

Figure 1 - Conceptual Framework

Source: done by the authors

So, the method is based on studying the impact of the independent variables, on the dependent variables in relation to the research questions.

BASE METHOD

The method adopted follows a typically qualitative and quantitative logic. The organizational climate survey aims to analyse employees' perception of it. With the information, HR can identify the reasons for dissatisfaction and the various points to be improved.

TARGET POPULATION

The target population was the workers of LAGOS-EM-FORMA, E.M., S.A. distributed in the following sectors/departments: Parking (17 workers), Municipal Pavilion and Swimming Pools (29 workers) and Municipal Stadium (7 workers), totalling 53 workers. A 5-point Likert scale was used, where 1) I completely disagree and 5) I completely agree. The following dimensions were addressed: Leadership, Training, Change, Communication.

DATA COLLECTION TECHNIQUE

When the data collection technique was used, a survey was carried out with all the company's workers. I didn't have much difficulty completing the questionnaire because the vast majority of people responded. I also had help from two colleagues to reach colleagues I didn't know.

An individual interview was also conducted (includes CEO; Financial, Administrative and Human Resources Director; Quality Manager/Human Resources support and 2 Coordinating Inspectors)

DATA PROCESSING TECHNIQUE

The data collected from the questionnaires were entered into an Excel database and later imported into the SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science) program, where statistical analysis was performed.

Content analysis of the interviews was also used (According to Laurence Bardin)

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The present point aims to analyse and discuss results, in order to find answers to the starting question identified in point 1 of this work. As mentioned in the previous point, we will carry out a qualitative analysis of the results, the collection of which used the following techniques: conducting exploratory interviews - which later gave rise to the questionnaire.

The concern regarding the collection of information that would provide reliable answers to the research question and information subject to using various sources of information, finding support in the design of a set of instruments for collecting information.

According to Bardin (2005, p. 117), “categorization is an operation of classifying constituent elements of a set, by differentiation and, subsequently, by regrouping according to genre (analogy), with previously defined criteria.”

Therefore, several readings were carried out from the interview transcripts to identify the most common themes. Once the recurring themes were identified, an initial coding was carried out to make it acceptable and understandable on quantitative bases in graph 1.

Graph 1 - Average Value per Variable

Source: Research Study results

It is possible to see that motivation on the part of the leader is fundamental to the work of the majority of workers in the organization. The employees' opinions are centred on point 5 (I totally agree).

Can also verify that, in general, workers 4) agree that the training received is sufficient to perform their work well. However, training could be a little more to perform their job well as there are some workers who 3) neither agree nor disagree.

It is verifiable that training programs effectively improve workers' skills and knowledge, and the vast majority agree with point 4), as can be seen in the choices made by them.

At this point change variable, there are very similar points, with point 3) I neither disagree nor agree and point 4) I agree that your company's recent changes to its work policy are fair and reasonable. However, it is clear that in point 2) I partially disagree and in point 5) I completely agree, these are 2 points in which the workers' opinions are exactly the same regarding the issue mentioned above.

Regarding the leadership skills demonstrated by the supervisor, it is verifiable that the workers demonstrate neither good nor bad qualities of the leadership skills demonstrated by the supervisor, mentioned in point 3). But we must mention that many workers have not expressed their opinion on this issue regarding the leadership of their current supervisor.

Table 1 - Correlation Matrix

Correlation Matrix		Motivation	Training	Change	Leadership	Communication
Motivation	R- Pearson	---				
	g	---				
	N	---				
	p - value	---				
Training	R- Pearson	-0,35	---			
	g	53	---			
	N	49	---			
	p - value	0,0006	---			
Change	R- Pearson	0,057	-0,25000	---		
	g	53	53	---		
	N	49	49	---		
	p - value	0,6	0,022	---		
Leadership	R- Pearson	0,31	-0,51	0,65	---	
	g	53	53	53	---	
	N	49	49	49	---	
	p - value	0,0038	0,0001	0,0001	---	
Communication	R- Pearson	0,14	-0,53	0,65	0,65	---
	g	53	53	53	53	---
	N	49	49	49	49	---
	p - value	0,21	0,0001	0,0001	0,0001	---
Purpose	R- Pearson	-0,34	0,54	-0,59	-0,65000	-0,53
	g	53	53	53	53	53
	N	49	49	49	49	49
	p - value	0,0012	0,0002	0,0003	0,0001	0,0002

Source: Research Study results

Here we show the importance of holding frequent meetings with employees. It is verifiable that the majority, in point 4) agree with the holding of frequent meetings with employees.

This variable shows us that communication between those responsible and employees is not always transparent, with point 3) neither disagreeing nor agreeing that communication is transparent between both, as well as point 4) agreeing that communication between those responsible and employees is transparent. these 2 points are very close to each other.

The vast majority of workers 3) neither disagree nor agree with the fact that they identify with the company's purposes. But in point 4) they agree by identifying with the company's purposes. It is noticeable that these two points are very close.

To this end, we focus on the elements that the process should include and the correlation that is established with Human Resources Management practices integrated into dimensions such as Change, Communication, Leadership, Training, among other aspects, knowing that the indices convey a holistic and non-segmented logic of action.

These points of interpretation of the results adhere to some elements evoked in the literature, considering that the combination of the aspects mentioned will be dispersed among several authors, also knowing that leadership is the greatest common denominator, Camara et al. (2007) and Cunha et al. (2005).

CONCLUSIONS

The study of change management allows us to extract two major fundamental ideas from the perspective of Human Resource Management, on the one hand the importance of human capital, that is, people/workers/collaborators, as they materialize changes and can be revealed as facilitating or inhibiting agents of the process, but on the other hand the importance of the role of the human resource management function and human resource practices, to the extent that organizational change and its improvement can be promoted by HRM by allowing the HR function to operate in a more strategic, inclusive and rational way.

The change management process will ensure competitiveness and responsiveness in accordance with market dynamics, given the systemic nature that the organization establishes with the environment, whether through contextual or transactional surroundings. In this context, change is an important and present characteristic in the life of an organization, whether at an operational or strategic level. Consequently, organizational change cannot be separated from its strategy and vice versa, which must be seen as clearly and objectively linked to the organization's strategy, since "successful long-term changes position change with strategy" (Nadler, 1989 cited in Ferreira and Martinez 2008:241).

However, from the literature review, elements such as concepts, techniques, approaches, tools and instruments of change management began to be made available, to establish the analogy and drive HRM values towards a better process condition.

According to what was explained in this work, it was possible to perceive the importance of the role of human resources management throughout the change management process in conciliation and collaboration with management. More than the role of human resource management practices implicit in values such as change, training, communication and leadership, it is important to rethink people management as an important component, which is why common sense should be used and, more than technical skills, the transversal skills of the people who promote the processes should be changed, with regard to the level of communication to facilitate participation, involvement, and mobilization of organizational agents based on elements such as, for example, the formation of teams, definition of an action plan, consolidation of change, among other important aspects. At the centre, responsibility is placed on the careful and sensitive guidance of change processes in a performance that implies competence to balance individual and organizational objectives and align towards achieving a strategy in which all parties involved come out on top, as only in this way will employees understand the change as necessary and aspirational for everyone and capable of developing competitiveness and success and, ultimately, organizational survival.

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